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POINT OF EMERGENCE – BODIES, CONTROL, AND COUNTER-MODULATION IN AI-DRIVEN SYSTEMS

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“Point of Emergence” acts as a kind of prolegomena to any consideration of what happens to the body in this phase of rapidly mutating socio-economic systems, whether we want to describe them as ‘technofeudalist,’ ‘neofeudalist,’ ‘technofascist,’ as the latest form of capitalism, or as ‘post-capitalist.’ Written as a contribution to the Post-Human Terrains, alternatives emerge on the one hand of the body as kind of infinite alterity (Guattari 1989, 1995) and on the other, in a reactionary cancellation of the animal/human divide, as “bodies [merely] for capital use” (Koložova 2025b). In this consolidation of an algorithmic-‘datalogical’-AI-driven-surveillance state, backed by ever-increasing numbers of police, especially in the U.S. but also elsewhere, resources of the body, the voice, and the ‘virtual,’ the traditional means of poetry, are broached as responses. This essay attempts to assay the conditions wherein the body-as-organism is immensely troubled if not cancelled, and “Embodiment can not be contained within the organic skin” (Clough 2018, p.xxxii), yet in its various forms remains an essential “biocommunist” circuit-breaker (Dyer-Witthford & Mularoni 2025)

In current, often virtual battlegrounds, different modes of the body are regularly challenged as an adequate or even partial substrate of resistance, remaining a “crucible” (Massumi 2015, p. 235). Surpassing and including previous modes of power Michel Foucault had labeled variously as sovereign, disciplinary, and then as a generalized “biopower” or “power over life” (Foucault 2008, pp. 304-308), Brian Massumi has outlined an “ontopower,” in an attempt to elucidate the intensified post-9/11 socio-political situation where “civilian life [becomes] a degree on the continuum of war” (Massumi 2015, p. 43). This “ontopower” is frequently preemptive, reorganizing on an ontological basis previous methods of control, creating a novel “ecology of powers” (Massumi 2015, vii). It paradoxically “brings to be what its apparatus captures” in a “field of power that is coextensive with the field of life” (Massumi 2015, pp. 233, 232). In this environmental modulation and preemption of affects, it is the body that becomes that “crucible,” an absolute hinge (Massumi 2015, p. 235). The operationalization of action-perception enacted by ontopower is often far too fast for conscious cognition. Hence the importance of

studies of nonconscious perception (see for instance Hayles 2017), and the ability to effect novel modulations or counter-modulations in response.

*from N. Katherine Hayles, Unthought:
The Power of the Cognitive Nonconscious (2017)*

Massumi's central examples were often based on U.S. military strategy, post 9/11, but he fingers a far more widespread phenomenon. With functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and positron emission topography (PET), visualizations of 'neural correlates' are produced that not only 'read' current thoughts, but also predict future ones. This kind of programming is based on the neuroscience Chris Frith describes, in that "we are not aware of the action we are about to perform until the brain has made an unconscious choice as to what that action should be" (qtd. in Väliaho 2014, p. 23). This uncovering of the plasticity of the brain is all too congruent with the needs of neoliberal systems in general, but especially their need to preempt and control any possible future. Here the shifting fields of neurology/the brain/the body (in its widest senses) play a central role.⁴¹

A "body without organs"

The French surrealist artist Antonin Artaud's "body without organs" was an invention or construction effected towards the end of a horrific nine-year asylum confinement, announced in Artaud's last radio address, *To have done with the judgment of god* (1947-1948), which also called out and denounced the perpetual conflict of the then brand new Cold War. This "body without organs" is articulated within what for Artaud was a nearly lifelong reference and elaboration, however cryptic, of "virtual" planes of existence, what he at one time called the "life plane" (Artaud 2004, p. 212). In a reading remarkably faithful to Artaud and his radicality, Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari famously appropriated this term in their *Capitalism and Schizophrenia* project (1972, 1980), to outline complex relations of the body and

⁴¹ As they continue to do in Massumi's study of the "full body" and "body without organs" in *The Personality of Power* (2025), a prospectus of contemporary fascism.

virtuality in conditions of contemporary capitalism. For Deleuze, this body without organs was a sort of “spherical body or scroll painting,” and “in this book everything happens” (Deleuze 2006, p.66; Deleuze 2002, p.123). As the virtual layers or virtual body that make any perception or action-perception possible, Artaud’s body without organs would be a key pivot in an era of “ontopower,” an age one could say Artaud prophesized (or recognized) with some ferocity in that last radio address. Its potential as a crucial source of counter-modulation was stressed most, perhaps, by Guattari. The “body without organs” for Guattari was heralded as the productive harbinger or basis of a post-media society. It was Guattari’s argument that within the domination of what he dubbed “integrated world capitalism” there is also the advent of the age of “planetary computerization”⁴² which creates “the possibility for creative and singularizing processuality to become the new fundamental point of reference” (Guattari 1998, p. 98). In this situation of potentially liberatory “existential re-appropriation and self-valorization” (Guattari 1998, p. 107) the “body without organs” becomes the primary meta-model⁴³: “With the figureless and foundationless Body without Organs of self-reference we see spreading before us an entirely different horizon, that of a new machinic processuality considered as the continual point of emergence of all forms of creativity” (Guattari 1998, p. 98).

From this perspective, the vicissitudes of the body are enmeshed in those of cycles of capital, so that “the tendencies of capitalism are moved toward the techno-ontological post-biological threshold” (Clough 2010, p. 221), whether this is the provision of turbine hearts, widespread accessibility of body modification, or the apparently ever-expanding international labor markets rooted in surrogacy, assisted reproduction, and experimental drug trials (Cooper and Waldby 2014). With the creation of a synthetic embryo with brain and beating heart from stem cells at University of Cambridge in August, 2022, an incipient era of ectogenesis can be added to these developments (Moran and Zhou 2023). Artificial intelligence (AI)-controlled brain implants that regularly use algorithms to transfer electrical pulses altering neural activity, treating mood disorders, are only one among a host of implants into the physical body that monitor or alter medical/bodily functions, acting as a prosthetic or delivering medicine.

It was in the gestation of such situations that Guattari developed his notion of assemblages, based on a modification of Francisco J. Varela’s development of the notion of autopoiesis. Articulating a generalized sense of “machinism,” beyond Norbert Wiener’s characterization of living systems as machines capable of feedback in first-order cybernetics, or Humberto Maturana and Varela’s version of autopoiesis that was only applicable to living systems, Guattari argued for a change in concept of the machine far beyond the “technical machine” into a “machinic assemblage” of “possible fields, of virtual as much as constituted elements” (Guattari, 1995, pp. 33-

⁴² Guattari authored some of the earliest trenchant analyses of globalisation, see “Plan for the Planet” (1979) and (with Eric Alliez) “Capitalistic Systems, Structures, and Processes” (1983) in Guattari’s *Molecular Revolution* (1984). For an elaboration of Guattari’s analyses, see Gary Genosko, “Guattari’s Contributions to the Theory of Semiocapitalism,” in *The Guattari Effect* (2011).

⁴³ Guattari contrasts “metamodelisation” to “modelisation” in that the former “uses terms to develop possible openings onto the virtual and onto creative processuality.” See Guattari 1995,

35). Whereas Varela defined machines as those which had a set of inter-relations of components independent of the components themselves (Varela 1979; Guattari 1995, p. 39), Guattari saw this as denying their materiality. The original definition of autopoiesis via Maturana and Varela for Guattari “lacks characteristics essential to living organisms, like the fact that they are born, die, and survive through genetic phylums” (Guattari 1995, p. 39). Challenging the distinction in Varela and Maturana of allopoietic machines (which produce something other than themselves) and p. 31.

The autopoietic cycle extended to the DNA/RNA/protein world. This is the autopoietic representation of the coded life autopoietic (which create, specify, and set their own organization and its limits), Guattari urged that autopoiesis be “rethought in terms of evolutionary, collective entities, which maintain diverse relations of alterity, rather than being implacably closed in on themselves” (Guattari 1995, pp. 39-40). While Varela himself moves away from the circularity of original notions of autopoiesis, thereby moving away from second-order cybernetics and contributing to the beginnings of third-order, Guattari’s perspective ushered in a “more collective machinism without delimited unity, whose autonomy accommodates diverse mediums of alterity” (Guattari 1995, p. 42). In fact, there can be no universal accounting or table for all these diverse registers of alterity, “because, in truth, their ontological modalities are infinite” (Guattari 1995, p. 45). As Keith Ansell Pearson has commented, “This is to think machinic autopoiesis as machinic heterogenesis and to introduce into the autopoietic model the necessary disequilibrium and far-from equilibrium conditions required for a truly creative model of evolution, in which evolution does not simply involve self-reproduction through the dissipation of outside forces and nullification of dimensions of alterity” (Pearson 1999, p. 170).⁴⁴ This last, more compact statement in *Chaosmosis* stems from Guattari’s extraordinary elaboration of “functors” and diagrams of multifarious webs of incorporeality and virtualities in his *Cartographies schizoanalytiques* (1989), models perhaps still not adequately appreciated or discussed (see Genosko 2022).⁴⁵

*fr*m Pier Luigi Luisi, “Autopoiesis: a review and a reappraisal,”
Naturwissenschaften (2003) 90: 49-59

⁴⁴ For a detailed comparison of Guattari’s with Varela’s versions of ‘autopoiesis,’ arguing Guattari’s is more useful or heuristic in the context of critical or anti-psychiatry, see Jay Murphy (2021a).

⁴⁵ Symptomatic, perhaps, is that in Elizabeth Grosz’ recounting of the philosophical itinerary of ‘incorporeals’ that create the framework or conditions for the functioning and understanding of material, corporeal realities, Guattari is only mentioned in connection with his collaborations with Deleuze (Grosz 2017).

	Expression actual discursive	Content virtual non-discursive
Possible	RHIZOMES Phylum actual possible abstract machinic discursivity	CONSTELLATIONS Universe virtual possible incorporeal complexity
Real	energetic-spatio-temporal discursivity Flux actual real COMPLEXIONS	chaosmic existential incarnation Territory virtual real CUT-OUTS

Assemblage of the four functional domains, from Félix Guattari, Schizoanalytic Cartographies (1989/2013)

“Name the system!”

Guattari applied his development of the notion of autopoiesis to subjectivation in general, as in the case of social movements, usually emphasizing there were no guarantees in profound moments of subjectivation, in terms of whether they resulted in greater emancipation, or, as in his example of the popular uprising of the 1979 Iranian revolution, coalesced into another kind of possible fascism. Although a popular slogan in the 1960’s New Left was “Name the system!” that has become increasingly more difficult to do. Marx arguably started from the category of individuals/populations, not the body, despite passing over the issue of populations rather quickly (Petersen 1988). The body remains key in increasingly murky delineations of stages of corporate capitalism or globalization that limn these new frontiers of what Foucault had dubbed “governmentality” (Foucault 1991, pp. 87-104). Given a contemporary economic landscape where exploitation often involves the multi-leveled collection of rents, not profit-making from wage labor as in the traditional Marxian schema, and where pre-capitalist modes of exploitation, from debt peonage to slavery, are in resurgence, some advocate ditching the term ‘capitalism’ altogether (for example, Wark 2019). Numerous others, such as economists Cédric Durand (2020) and Yanis Varoufakis (2021) insist on the new label “Techno-feudalism” that has reached a degree of popular discussion (Timberlake 2022; Harris 2022), so that it is debated in the pages of *New York Magazine*, not only *New Left Review* (see Morozov 2022, Dean 2022, Strum 2022). As Evgeny Morozov notes, the YouTube debate on the topic between Varoufakis and Slavoj Žižek drew over 300,000 viewers in just three weeks (Morozov 2022). In defense of the term, Marxist political scientist Jodi Dean concludes, Neofeudalism speaks to that. (Dean 2022).

The counter-revolution of neoliberalism has been a process of privatization, fragmentation and separation, in the name of a hyper-individualized freedom that resembles the “dot-like isolation” of the *Grundrisse*’s “free” worker. Today’s proletarians are caught up in a new kind of serfdom, dependent on networks and

practices through which rents are extracted at every turn. When production is insufficiently profitable for accumulation, holders of capital seek returns elsewhere. In the process, they further the dynamic of separation and induce new dependencies, which require a new name.

Others, such as Wolfgang Streck (Streck 2016) and economist Michael Hudson (Hudson 2012) have talked about contemporary political economy in terms of “neo-feudalism” for nearly a decade, or more. It has fed into Hudson’s most recent analysis of newly forming geopolitical blocs (from the resource/energy wars underlying the Ukraine/Russia conflict to China’s vast Silk Road initiative and increasing cooperation and bi-lateral trade among the BRICS countries) as representing conflicts between the respective protagonists of financial capitalism, industrial capitalism, and socialism (Hudson 2022).

***Columbia University strike, April, 1968, New York, New York, photo:
Gene Kappock/NY Daily News Archive/Getty Images***

As a term, it remains to be seen whether “techno-feudalism” will successfully supplant the perhaps equally dubious “cognitive capitalism” (Vercellone 2006; Moulier-Boutang 2012) that largely grew out of some of the analyses cited here, from Italy’s *autonomia* theorists. As again, Jodi Dean points out, the notion of “cognitive capitalism” arguably “makes the world appear smarter than it is, as if intelligence replaced manufacturing when in fact manufacturing was pushed out of some countries and onto others in the search for ever cheaper labor,” implying “affective labor is something new” while it “overplays immateriality even as it brings materiality, meat, bones, and blood back in via emphasis on brains” (Dean 2013, p. 70). For his part, George Caffentzis has reminded us that there has been, practically from its inception, a “long tradition connecting capitalism with cognition, rationality and the abstract quantitative spirit” (Caffentzis 2013a, p. 96). Preceding the popularity of the term “cognitive capitalism” there was already a robust discussion of the “knowledge economy,” in academic, and popular business circles,

as well as in reports by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the World Bank (Caffentzis 2013a, p. 76). The earlier versions of “cognitive capitalism” included notions of the “intellectual worker” constituting a division of labor and a managerial class that in reality drove capitalist systems and as the decision-makers often benefitted more than the traditional capitalist class. This stratum would be, as in the title of a 1979 anthology on this “professional-managerial class,” “between labor and capital” (Walker 1979). This is the widespread thesis of the “managerial revolution” from James Burnham (1941) to Peter Drucker (1993), what John Kenneth Galbraith termed the middle- and upper-management “technostructure” (Galbraith 1967), that also has crucial versions emerging from anarchist and alternative Marxist traditions.⁴⁶

Regardless of what terminology we decide to employ, many of these quandaries are already outlined in what Marx in his *Grundrisse* (1857)⁴⁷ described as capital’s successful subsumption of labor, the increasing concentration of general knowledge and science in the fixed capital of machinery that looms over the individual worker, producing new heights and extremities in exploitation while maximizing the socialization of production to the extent that labor-value as a quantitative means of measurement becomes hopelessly obsolete. It can be argued, as has The Invisible Committee, that the very definition of capitalism revolves around its ability in “rendering accountable whatever is not yet accountable...capitalism is the universal expansion of measurement” (The Invisible Committee 2017, p. 98). Marx foresaw this situation when “the value objectified in machinery appears as a presupposition against which the value-creating power of the individual labor capacity is an infinitesimal, vanishing magnitude” (Marx 1973, p. 694). Thus, contrary to much that Marx wrote elsewhere, the course of capitalist development tends in itself to do away with the workings of the law of value,⁴⁸ by making scientific knowledge and its applied organization in production the principal productive force. This has the effect of reproducing the factory model across society so that, as Toni Negri and Michael Hardt have written, “in the same moment when theory no longer sees labor, labor has everywhere become *the* common substance” (Hardt and Negri 1994, p. 11).

Marx’s “separation”

In this transition from formal to real subsumption of labor, capital appears omnipotent and all-pervasive, provoking a crisis of extraordinary “separation” (Marx 1967, p. 33) felt in every aspect of social, economic and political life. This situation of extreme schizophrenia writ large, to return to the locus of the body, Patricia Clough argued, “techno-ontological post-biological threshold[s]” (Clough 2010, p. 221) were

⁴⁶ Donald C. Hodges in *America’s New Economic Order* (1996) provides a comprehensive survey of myriad post-capitalist theories (that ‘capitalists’ are not the primary beneficiaries of the corporate order). These date at least from the 1930’s and ‘40s with thinkers who concluded that Nazi Germany, Stalin’s Russia, and Franklin Roosevelt’s New Deal USA had all, in their different ways, put an end to the essentials of capitalism as it had been defined.

⁴⁷ In terms of Marxology, it is in the *Grundrisse* that it has been argued Marx moved decisively beyond Hegelian schemas, see for example Nesbitt (2022). This is further developed in Nesbitt’s accounting of materialism and dialectics in the work of Louis Althusser, where he argues the Spinozist influence far outweighs the Hegelian in *Capital*, see *Reading Capital’s Materialist Dialectic* (2025).

⁴⁸ As Marx writes elsewhere in the same section, ‘Capital thus works towards its own dissolution as the form dominating production.’ p. 700.

being surpassed. The mutations of the body and its biological existence, and not only or merely vagaries of its desire, form this agenda.

frm <https://www.signalsmatter.com/wall-street-disaster/>

Correspondingly, critiques of the notion of the “body without organs” that reduce it to a certain question of desire, will miss its continuing importance. This seems the case with Alexander Galloway when in his *Laruelle* (2014) he postulates a difference between the analysis of the Deleuze of 1972 (the problematic of desire and “body without organs” in *Anti-Oedipus*) and of 1990 (author of “Postscript on the Societies of Control”), arguing the later writing supplants the politics of the earlier one. Yet when the ‘later’ Deleuze asks, “Is not life this capacity to resist force?” (Deleuze 1988, p. 93) this remains resistance that relies on the virtual substratum of the “body without organs”.

Artaud, in his terror of being reduced to the physical body, doubled it in a “virtual” body, as if it were alongside the “actual” body, without touching it at any point. Deleuze and Guattari followed this very closely, as when they wrote the “body without organs” “had nothing to do with the body itself, or an image of the body” (Deleuze and Guattari 1977, p. 8). In our current plethora of prostheses of the body and digital/media connectivity of our nervous/sensory systems, it only makes sense to realize, Patricia Clough writes, “Embodiment can not be contained within the organic skin” (Clough 2018, p. xxxii). In her version of this dilemma, Clough continues, “We are proposing that there is an abstracting of affect to affect-itself, which disregards the bounded-ness of the human body, thus troubling the conception of the body as body-as-organism” (Clough 2018, p. 7). This “abstracting of affect” replaces, in an economy where surplus value is extracted in an information or data-economy, the abstracting of labor-power Marx analyzed in the 19th century. As a passage or historical phase, this parallels what French economist Frédéric Lordon termed “[M]oving from the economics of surplus-value to the politics of capture” (Lordon 2014, p. 118). George Caffentzis is among those who have argued (against Michael

Hardt and Antonio Negri) that “affective” or “immaterial labor” can still be measured as exploitation (Caffentzis 2013b, pp. 176-200; Caffentzis 2005); whereas in the 19th century thermodynamics provided a uniform measure of energy and thus a yardstick for extraction of surplus value from the industrial working class, with the invention of the computer, computational procedures or cybernetics now provide that same function.

As Caffentzis maintains, the definition of “immaterial labor” in Hardt and Negri’s first salvo of their tetralogy, *Empire* (Hardt & Negri 2001, p. 293), can be found wanting. Caffentzis writes, what appear to be “immaterial” products of labor are the result of pattern production that can be accomplished by machines (whether they be composed of wood, iron, and paper cards, and powered by heat engines or of plastic, silicon, and copper and powered by electric currents). These machines are fully “physical,” in the usual sense of the word, as are the patterns they produce and, most importantly, reproduce. For at the core of capitalist commodity production is the reproduction of a pattern, whether it be “com- posed” of pure silk or pure electrons. (Caffentzis 2013b, p. 199)

Marx’s theory of machines is not wrong so much as it is incomplete, having been formulated before the advent of the Turing machine, the basis for computation invented by Alan Turing 1936-37. Yet the opposition Hardt and Negri make between “intelligent manipulation” and “routine tasks” (Hardt & Negri 2001, p. 293), Caffentzi argues is made moot by the computer, which operates via projects that are eminently analytic and symbolic, yet are no less routine for all that. Their phrase “immaterial labor” thus serves to only obfuscate what can be common characteristics of labor shared between housework and computer programming, for example.

In what Clough – with a group of her graduate students in a 2015 essay – dubbed “the datalogical turn” (in Clough 2018, pp. 94-114), the conjunction of myriad computational technologies, digital media, algorithmic and other “other-than-human agencies” (xxi), present a type of “governmentality” that they argued supersedes “biopower.” Drawing on the work of Luciana Parisi on algorithmic architecture (Parisi 2013) and Randy Martin on financialization and the logic of derivatives (Martin 2007, 2015), Clough credits algorithms as spatio-temporal structures in their own right, with the potential of “changing parameters in real time” (Clough 2018, p. xxi). As Parisi described it, “the residual power of algorithms...are able to unleash novelty in biological, physical, and mathematical forms” (qtd. in Clough 2018, p. 95). For Clough this algorithmic and financial indeterminacy creates a transition to “affective measuring” (Clough 2018, p. xx). One can argue the turn to affect theory in the first instance was a consequence of the extreme precarity operating in neoliberal economies (see Moore 2014), with the concern with measurement never far away, of which the Quantified Self movement is only one example, where managers have taken a growing interest in such tools as daily activity tracking software and other wearable digital recording equipment such as Sensecam, Subcam sensecams, automas, memoto and audio-visual recorders. These products are used for first person perspective digital ethnographies, lifelogging, and self-tracking

of both mental and physical activities in conjunction with productivity-related measures. (Moore 2014, 12)

But for Clough, analyses such as Caffentzis' that exploitation remains eminently measurable, are at fault in an even larger sense, for not understanding that digital technologies can 'see' information at all scales of matter itself, that is, that "matter is self-measuring" (Clough 2018, n. 4 p. 168).

Here Clough seems to welcome the paranoid actuality of the digital, with its ability to "encode and simulate anything whatsoever in the universe," with its "capacity to divide things and make distinctions between them," being that which "makes it possible to make any distinction at all" (Galloway 2014, p. xxiv). In contrast to a blithe acceptance of the digital, the refusal of work in the autonomist tradition is also a refusal of imposed measure. As Antonio Negri wrote, resistance embodied in affect, "poses action beyond every measure that power does not contain in itself, in its own structure and in the continuous restructurings that it constructs" (Negri 1999, 85). Alex Galloway reminds us of the larger issue that "Digitality is much more capacious than the computer, both historically because there simply is no history without digitality, but also conceptually, because the digital is a basic ingredient within ontology, politics, and most everything in between" (Galloway 2014, pp. xxxiv). There are numerous dissents from Clough's notion of self-measurement, whether Neils Bohr's view of the fluctuations of dynamic matter as a kind of indeterminism basic to physical reality or Ilya Prigogine's investigation of how different mathematical conceptualizations of an identical problem produce comparably valid but not equivalent representations. Yet there is the sense, as Jed Brody writes in *Quantum Entanglement*, that "measurement creates objectively real states" (Brody 2020, p. 140). This creates one possible explanation of why entangled photons, for instance, are not observable on a macroscopic scale,

The entanglement is *severed* the instant it takes effect, exactly when a measurement of *one* photon creates a definite polarization for *both*. This provides a possible explanation for why we don't observe entanglement on a macroscopic scale: the very many particles making up macroscopic objects are constantly interacting and in some sense "measuring" one another, thereby disentangling as fast as they entangle. (Brody 2020, pp. 73-74)

In parallel, or not, is Guattari's sense of the paradox of fractal scales, which can only be understood if one is released from interpreting them in terms of "energetico-spatial-temporal coordinates" (Guattari 1995, pp. 50-51). Ultimately, this is in league with the untenability, what can only be a "productive paradox," of transcendence and immanence (Massumi 2002, p. 38). So these dynamics increasingly broach metaphysical questions. Arguably this is the case from the very beginning of Marx's description of capitalism, with its *ex nihilo* creation of surplus value, a kind of bastard child from the Judeo-Christian tradition (Dussel 2009).

Beyond the organism

To return to the socio-economic situation, any sense of a separate organism in this state of affairs is swept up in circuits of "bio-cybernetic capital" (Rajan 2006) where "preservation of 'vivified matter in the face of adversity and a universal

tendency toward disorder' is too conservative a goal" (Parisi & Terranova 2000). Guattari could postulate Artaud's "body without organs" as "the continual point of emergence of all forms of creativity" (Guattari 1998, p. 98), due to his vastly expanded notion of autopoiesis that doesn't obey the usual laws of thermodynamics, projecting instead a Spinozistic–Nietzschean infinity, where the increasing obsolescence of the notion of the individual organism, was no barrier. Arguably, Artaud's ferocious assault on forms of representation, especially in the last two years of his life, was a premature attack on the omnipresence of the digital (Murphy 2021b, pp. 148-149). For Artaud's autochthonic "body without organs," its "foundation" is a "perpetual variable" (Artaud XX 1984, p. 66), which is never a world of meter and measurement (Artaud XXII 1986, p. 436). Artaud is only one of the poets Jean Baudrillard, for instance, insisted created a kind of metamorphosis, a "metamorphosis allows you to move from one form to another without bringing in value" (Baudrillard 1996, p. 48). Likewise, Nikolaj Lübecker has recently claimed the senses of subjectivation in poets like Paul Verlaine, Charles Baudelaire, and Stéphane Mallarmé can only be understood in their full ecological sense, or as with the evocation of the "virtual" in Mallarmé, in the socio-economic-technological conditions – and with the theoretical tools – of the 21st century (Lübecker 2022). In this light, with his conjuring of virtual dimensions an integral feature of what Tristan Tzara termed his "combat," Arthur Rimbaud's demolition of the representational can also be seen with renewed eyes.

Such experiments in "metamorphosis," pace Baudrillard or Deleuze and Guattari, of course can hardly be limited to symbolism and post-symbolism, rather than almost infinitely multiplied. As Guattari pointed out, "for apprehending the diversity of the modes of subjectification and semiotization," there are no better guides than the "'works' of Henri Michaux and to the American writers of the 'beat generation'" (Guattari 2011, pp. 231-2). As a recent example, one can look to the ongoing and early writing/spoken word/performance experiments (now legion) with AI programs like GPT-2 by Mark Amerika, that in its "lingual spontaneity" provide a further dimension to what Jack Kerouac had called "sketching" in a "materialist remix praxis" also linked to avant-garde traditions (Amerika 2022, pp. 32, 34).

For his part, Artaud claimed he was "a being which nature has never been able to entirely capture" (Artaud XX 1984, p. 10). "Nature" is not able to "capture" Artaud, since he is remaining as faithful as possible to the fluxes of destratification, the liminality in-between the respective limits of destratification – on one end the "body without organs," and on the other the organism, neither of which exist. Both are "limits of the opposed processes of stratification and destratification," a stratum itself being a ratio of capture versus escape (Protevi 2001, p. 38). Organs, are distributed across the "body without organs," but "they distribute themselves independently of the form of the organism" (Deleuze & Guattari 1987, p. 164). Their organic organization into the system of the organism is precisely what Artaud condemns as the "judgment of god" (Deleuze & Guattari 1987, p. 158). Given some of the looming prognostications concerning the current political economy and Artificial Intelligence (see Dyer-Witthford et al 2019, Witthford & Mularoni 2025;

Pasquinelli 2015), what Guattari called a “continual point of emergence” will remain a matter of complexified, ever intensifying struggle.

Newly discovered photo of Arthur Rimbaud, November 1, 1873, by Ernest Balthazar

The General Conditions of Production in Historical Perspective

Time Period	17th C–late 18th C	Late 18th C–mid 19th C	19th C	Late 19th C–late 20th C	1970s–2010s	2010s–?	??
Epoch of Production	Mercantile Capital	Manufacture	Industrial Capitalism		Cybernetic Capitalism		
Period of Production		Manufacture	Large-scale industry	Fordism	Post-Fordism	Actually-existing AI-capitalism	AI-capitalism
Production Technologies and Organization	Handicrafts, cooperation, hand tools	Division of labour, hand tools	Industrial machinery, division of labour	Taylorism, assembly line, mass production	Flexible production (mass customization), supply chain	Narrow AI	
Type of Subsumption ¹	Formal Subsumption		Real Subsumption		'Hyper-Subsumption' ²		
General Conditions of Production	Canals, sail shipping, colonial markets, roads, draft animals, stage coaches	Division of labour, asphalt roads, canals, sail shipping, colonial markets and system	Steam power, machine tooling, production of machines by machines, railways, prime movers, river steamers, steamships, world market, telegraph, imperialism	Electrical power, telegraph, radio, television, automobile, Bretton Woods (GATT, WB, IMF), world market	Global and regional trade agreements (NAFTA, WTO), ICTs, networks, electronic financial markets, logistics, global supply chains, software, information, bar codes, scanning technology, container shipping and intermodal transportation, process mapping	The cloud, big data, platforms, sensors, smartphones and personal computers, GPS, narrow AI, broadband internet, web	AI autonomous vehicles, smart cities, digital personal assistants, increasingly advanced AI, production of AI by AI, 3D printing

Notes:

1. There are different interpretations of subsumption as either a logical or historical category. While this table adopts the latter, we do not all agree on using subsumption as a way to periodize the capitalist mode of production. The difference in interpretation of subsumption is related to how *Capital* is interpreted: (1) as a work depicting the historical development of capitalism (see e.g. Ernest Mandel 1990); or (2) as a theoretical analysis of capitalism that examines the essential determinants of capitalism, those elements which must remain the same regardless of all historical variations so that we may speak of “capitalism” as such¹ (Heinrich 2012: 31). For a discussion on the historical vs. logical interpretation of subsumption, see Endnotes (2010).

2. The concept of ‘hyper-subsumption’ is similar to Stiegler’s concept of grammatization.

from Nick Dyer-Whiteford, Atle Mikkola Kjøsén, and James Steinhoff, Inhuman Power: Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Capitalism (2019)

It is a struggle that may have to jettison other short-lived short-hands, no matter how adequate or inadequate, such as ‘technofeudalism,’⁴⁹ or better yet, “technofascism,” given the agglomeration of power of Palantir, Blackrock, Meta, Apple, TikTok, Oracle, Open AI, Microsoft, Amazon, Google, and others paired with the ongoing near decimation of the federal government in the U.S., spearheaded by Elon Musk’s teen raiders in DOGE (Department of Government Efficiency). The unprecedented taking over of government functions by AI is part of a larger strategy of mega-concentration. “If they have their way,” journalist Chris Hedges summarizes, “all commercial technology will be completely folded into the national security state – acting blatantly as the new infrastructure for techno-authoritarian rule. The underlying idea behind this new system is ‘pre-crime,’ or the use of mass surveillance to designate people criminals *before* they’ve committed any crime” (Hedges & Webb 2025). AI is characterized by billions upon billions in investment, with very little real profit – only five percent of ChatGPT users would pay for the service, yet that has been more than made up by its integration into any conceivable military, intelligence, and surveillance function. This is a far from separate development from the ICE/DHS onslaught in the American streets. As organizer, teacher, and blogger J.P. Hill writes in an acute column, “The only way for AI to succeed is for it to be forced on us and for profits to be forced out of consumers. And with the entire economy resting more and more on AI investments, a crisis for AI becomes a crisis for capitalism. That is exactly where fascism comes in, attacking democracy in order to rescue capitalism through force” (Hill 2025). “The fascist strain,” Hill judged, already a strong force for corporations like Palantir that first gestated via contracts with the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA), “is now dominant.” The July 2025 Congressional budget bill for ICE and border security included contracts for iris scanners, facial-recognition apps, phone-hacking software, cellphone location data, and “major spending also on detention centers, air transport and guns” – upgrading the surveillance capacity of the state for everything from facial-recognition software to social media posts and tracking physical movements (Dou 2025). This autonomic accelerationism is already creating some of the more bizarre forms of what Marx had called social relations transformed into the “fantastic form of a relation between things” (Marx 1975, p. 83), the ever-present threat of bodies becoming simply “bodies for capital use” (Kolozova 2015b). In other words, in the Burroughsian “war universe” (Burroughs 1991) consistent combat.

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⁴⁹ For a recent attack on the harmfulness of this term, see Katerina Kolozova (2025a), “No Such Thing as Techno-Feudalism,” Katerina Kolozova Substack, 28 March, <https://substack.com/home/post/p-160059741>. For Kolozova any adequate appraisal of capitalism understands it is impossible for it to proceed backwards, and any momentous pronouncement of the ‘death of capitalism’ must be indebted to Marx, even if it is a refutation of his work.

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